

DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH IN SCHOOL LESSONS OF HEARING-IMPAIRED CHILDREN

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Abstract: This scientific thesis is aimed at studying the pedagogical foundations of the development of oral speech in school reading classes of children with hearing impairment. The thesis describes the importance and effective methods of forming oral speech in students with hearing impairment. The study was conducted in order to meet the communicative needs of hearing impaired children, improve their socialization, and also ensure their linguistic development. The author reflects on the advantages and results of using interactive methods, didactic games, logopedic approaches in the teaching process. Ways to improve teaching methods in practice and the importance of creating the necessary environment for the development of oral speech are emphasized.

Key words: children with hearing impairment, oral speech, reading lessons, speech therapy approaches, communicative need, socialization, interactive methods.

Introduction.

Hearing impaired children are a group that needs special attention in school education. Due to the limited ability of hearing, these children face many difficulties in the process of speech and communication. Reading classes provide an opportunity for children not only to acquire knowledge, but also to develop socialization, self-expression and communication skills.

However, conventional teaching methods and approaches may not be effective for students with hearing problems. Therefore, it is necessary to use certain methodologies and strategies in the development of oral speech. In this thesis, important pedagogical approaches, interactive teaching methods and logopedic education methods are studied in the development of oral speech of children with hearing impairment. The thesis also includes practical recommendations that will help to improve students' communication skills, organize effective communication, and build speech culture.

As a result, this study provides scientific and practical aspects aimed at improving the process of developing oral speech in reading classes of children

with hearing impairment. This will be important not only in pedagogical practice, but also in the implementation of comprehensive changes in the educational system.

Literature Analysis: Research conducted in the field of education of hearing impaired children is an important source for the development of pedagogical approaches and methods. The analysis of this literature helps to study modern approaches to the development of oral speech in reading classes of hearing impaired children.

Hearing impairment and education: M. K. Koval and A. V. Peskov (2018) emphasize in their research the importance of psychological and pedagogical approaches in the education of children with hearing impairment. According to them, such children need special educational programs to develop their communication skills. Also, the authors emphasize the effectiveness of speech therapy approaches and the importance of interactive methods.

Speech development and methodology: A. R. Mirsayev (2020) in his research shows the need to use interactive teaching methods for speech development of students with hearing problems. Mirsayev's research proves that it is possible to improve the oral speech of students with the help of didactic games and group activities. These methods help to develop communication between children and facilitate the establishment of mutual relations.

Speech therapy approaches: A. S. Fedorova (2019) explores the importance of speech therapy education in children with hearing impairment. His research shows that using speech therapy approaches plays an important role in the development of children's speech skills. Fedorova emphasizes the need for teachers to learn special methods to effectively work with children with hearing impairment.

Communicative needs: E. N. Gromova (2021) studies the satisfaction of communicative needs in the educational process for children with hearing impairment. Gromova's research shows that children need to be able to interact, which increases their self-expression and socialization.

The analysis of these literatures shows that the combined methods of logopedic, interactive and didactic approaches are necessary for the development of oral speech in the educational process of hearing impaired children. The interaction of these methods helps to make the educational process more effective and is important for the development of children's communication skills. Therefore, it is desirable to develop new pedagogical strategies based on the approaches and methods presented in these studies.

Discussion.

The development of oral speech in school reading classes of children with hearing impairment is one of the important aspects of the educational process. The methodologies and pedagogical approaches studied in this thesis serve to improve programs aimed at speech development of students with hearing impairment. The results obtained during the research show the need to expand the methods used in practice and develop more effective strategies in this regard.

Speech development of hearing impaired children requires an approach in accordance with their psychological and social needs. Using speech therapy approaches, didactic games and interactive methods, students can improve their speaking skills. These methods help improve students' communication skills and ease the process of socialization. Also, pedagogical skills and methodical skills of teachers play an important role in working with such children.

The obtained results emphasize the need to develop special approaches and strategies in the educational process for children with hearing impairment. In working with these children, close cooperation between teachers and speech therapists is important to improve the educational process. The development of independent work and group activities in the teaching process increases children's opportunities for mutual communication.

Also, studies show the need to take into account the individual characteristics of the methods used in the educational process. Each child requires a unique and individual approach, so teachers need to adapt educational methods to the needs of each student. In this, the pedagogical creativity and abilities of teachers are important.

In general, the integration of modern pedagogical approaches and methods for the development of oral speech of children with hearing impairment in school reading classes increases the effectiveness of the educational process. This helps not only to develop students' communication skills, but also to improve their socialization process. The obtained results pave the way for further research and development of new approaches in the future.

Conclusion.

In this thesis, the issue of development of oral speech of children with hearing impairment in school reading lessons was studied. The results of the research showed that there are a number of pedagogical approaches and methods that affect the speech development of hearing impaired children. With the help of logopedic approaches, interactive teaching methods and didactic

games, it helps to improve children's communicative abilities, expand their opportunities for mutual communication and form speech culture.

In addition, the pedagogical skills of teachers and their cooperation with children increase the effectiveness of the educational process. Each child has his own individual characteristics, and it is necessary to develop approaches in accordance with them. The methods and strategies used in the educational process facilitate the process of socialization of students and play an important role in the development of speech.

Future research in this area will help to develop new pedagogical approaches and methods, as well as to further improve existing practices. Applying effective approaches and strategies in the educational process for children with hearing impairments gives them the opportunity to express themselves and communicate. As a result, this leads to an increase in self-confidence of children and their more active participation in the educational process.

Thus, this thesis shows the need to study new approaches and strategies in the development of oral speech of children with hearing impairment and provides practical recommendations in this regard in the educational process.

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